

Abstract

Analysis of support in the identification of cognitive distortions in young adults through an ad hoc video game

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Abstract: Cognitive distortions (CDs) are defined as identifiable thinking errors [1], self-affirmations based on erroneous interpretations of reality [2]. In most cases, it is very difficult for people to identify by themselves the presence of CDs among his thoughts. As it is a factor of vulnerability to mental disorders such as depression and anxiety [3], identifying its presence is a basic principle for the treatment of these disorders [1]. In Mexico, although there are medical centers for mental health care in some centralized areas of the country [4], it is a reality that lack of access, shortage of human resources and stigmas on the subject in Mexican culture [1,5] limit the care that can be provided to the general population. Under these circumstances, serious video games represent a very attractive alternative in terms of availability, scope and ease for work with mental health issues [6]. This work proposes the use of an ad hoc digital therapy tool, focused on the self-identification of cognitive distortions by the user, working with the three most common CDs in a population of undergraduate students[7]. It is estimated that through the use of this tool, users are able to identify the presence of CDs, reinforcing their ability to reflect and pay attention to them. The self-reported questionnaire CD-QUEST [8] is used as a tool to measure the ability to identify DC of the subjects, analyzing the impact of the use of a serious video game in the rational emotive-behavioral therapy model.

Keywords: Cognitive Distortions; Mental Health; Video Games

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by an Institutional Review Board of the Departamento de Sistemas y Computación of the Tecnológico Nacional de México/IT de Mérida.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank the AAAIMX student chapter and MAIA platform for the support to collect the data used in this work.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Citation: Matos-Pech;

Orozco-del-Castillo . *ICAIMH Abstract*

Proceedings 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7955668>

Published: February, 2023

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